

UNVEILING STIGMA: ADDRESSING MENSTRUAL HYGIENE AND HEALTH IN THE INDIAN CONTEXT

Apoorva Ramachandra | Ablaz Schemnad | Moumita Barman
Meenakshi Gupta | Aditi Sharma | Laldinmoi Pangamte

WORKING PAPER

ISSUE-03 | July-2024 | VOLUME-04

In collaboration
with

CDPP

CENTRE FOR
DEVELOPMENT
POLICY AND
PRACTICE

UNVEILING STIGMA :

ADDRESSING MENSTRUAL HYGIENE AND HEALTH IN THE INDIAN CONTEXT

Apoorva Ramachandra | Ablaz Schemnad | Moumita Barman |
Meenakshi Gupta | Aditi Sharma | Laldinmoi Pangamte

WORKING PAPER SERIES

ISSUE - 03 | JULY - 2024 | VOLUME-04

In Collaboration
with

गूज..

GOONJ.. a voice, a n effort
www.goonj.org

Abstract

This paper tries to bring out the critical importance of addressing menstrual health and hygiene by considering its significant impact on individuals' well-being, societal norms, and environmental sustainability. It highlights how societal norms, cultural practices, and institutional biases hinder access to necessary care and emphasises the need for a comprehensive approach that goes beyond hygiene issues to encompass social, psychological, and gender-diverse needs. Utilising data from the National Family Health Surveys (NFHS), it discusses the current state of menstrual health and hygiene in India, noting positive shifts in societal attitudes and product usage while also acknowledging persistent challenges like inadequate access to WASH facilities.

Moreover, the paper delves into the critical issue of menstrual waste management, stressing the environmental and health risks associated with improper disposal practices. It discusses various disposal techniques and the need for comprehensive strategies to promote proper waste management, destigmatise menstruation, and uphold the dignity of sanitation workers. Additionally, government initiatives and policies aimed at improving menstrual health in India are discussed, such as the Draft Menstrual Hygiene Policy. It acknowledges the strengths of the policy while addressing some limitations and challenges in implementation. Additionally, the paper traces how Goonj's initiative of "Not just a piece of cloth" has broken many menstrual challenges.

Overall, the paper places an emphasis on the importance of broadening the conversation surrounding menstrual health and hygiene to include experiential aspects, cultural stigmas, and the needs of gender-diverse menstruators. It highlights the need for comprehensive support and sustainable waste management practices to prioritise health, dignity, and environmental concerns.

Keywords: Menstrual Hygiene, Dignity, Menstrual Waste, Stigma, Sanitary Pads, Menstrual Waste, Cloth Pads

Note: Goonj hosted their annual event, "Menstruation Dialogue 2024" on May 28, 2024, in collaboration with the Centre for Development Policy and Practice, National Foundation for India, and Ashoka. This paper incorporates various points and recommendations raised during the panel discussions.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	I
1. Introduction	01
2. Data insights	02
3. Challenges with Maintaining Menstrual Hygiene and Health	07
3.1 Intersections of Menstrual Health and Hygiene	07
3.2 Neglected Demographics and Scenarios	11
4. Menstrual Waste Management	15
5. India's Stance on Menstrual Health and Hygiene	16
5.1 Goonj's Comprehensive Idea for Scale	17
5.2 Upcoming Initiative: The Draft Menstrual Hygiene (MH) Policy	20
6. International Perspectives	24
7. Way Forward	28
REFERENCES	31

1. Introduction

Understanding the importance of an individual's menstrual health is crucial to their well-being and that of their family and community. Unfortunately, in many parts of the world, including India, societal norms, cultural practices, and institutional biases often hinder individuals from accessing the necessary menstrual health care. This persistent issue of inadequate menstrual health and hygiene management continues to be one of the most pressing development challenges today.

Menstruation is a natural physiological process that occurs in adolescent girls, premenopausal women, transgender men, and non-binary individuals of reproductive age. The WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme in 2012 gave a broad definition of Menstrual Hygiene Management as: "Women and adolescent girls use hygienic materials to absorb or collect menstrual blood, which can be changed in privacy as often as necessary for the duration of a menstrual period, use soap and water for washing the body as required, and have access to safe and convenient materials to dispose of used materials. They understand the basic facts linked to the menstrual cycle and how to manage it with dignity and without discomfort or fear." The process of menstruation requires the availability of resources for absorbing or collecting menstrual blood, promoting personal hygiene, and ensuring the proper disposal of waste, ideally in a private setting.

This definition is widely used, and discussions around challenges of menstruation are restricted to hygiene issues; however, it needs to go beyond hygiene and include social and psychological components, the health impact of menstrual experience, and gender-diverse populations (Hennegan et al., 2021).

A more inclusive definition is that menstrual health encompasses the physical, mental, and social well-being throughout the menstrual cycle of women, girls, and all other individuals who menstruate. It involves access to accurate information, supportive hygiene practices, timely care for discomforts, a stigma-free environment, and the freedom to participate fully in all aspects of life without discrimination or violence (Hennegan et al., 2021).

So, it becomes necessary to understand where India stands on various aspects related to menstrual health and hygiene and identify places that require attention. On those lines, this paper explores data on the usage of menstrual products using National Family Health Survey (NFHS) data, the challenges and intersections of maintaining menstrual health and hygiene, menstrual waste management, what India is doing to address the challenges, international perspectives, and the way forward.

2. Data Insights

In recent years, the societal mindset and taboos associated with menstruation and the usage of hygienic menstrual products have been reduced over the years in the country. The more favourable attitude can be connected to the significant increase in the policy and public discussions around menstruation. The national-level data sets show a trend towards a positive direction. Mass media and audio-visual entertainment platforms have a key role to play in this progress. However, we as a country still have a long way to go to attain a safe, secure, and hygienic practice of menstrual health management. Various characteristics, such as level of education, wealth, place of residence, etc., give varying trends in the usage of hygienic menstrual products. The following section will address some of the indicators from the NFHS reports in its fourth and fifth rounds, conducted in 2015–16 and 2019–21, respectively.

The NFHS data showed a significant jump in the share of young women (aged 15–24 years) using a hygienic method of menstrual protection over the last few years. More than three-fourths of them use a hygienic product for menstrual protection, which can be sanitary napkins, locally prepared napkins, tampons, and menstrual cups (NFHS-5, 2019–21). Even though residents in the urban sector are relatively better off, the rural-urban divide in the usage of hygienic products has seen a major reduction of 12% from 2015–16 to 2019–21. Moreover, the highest improvement in the use of hygienic products was seen among the poorest section in the same period, a rise from 21.1% to 53.6%. On the contrary, despite the satisfactory advancements, the usage of cloth remains prevalent in the country irrespective of socioeconomic characteristics, with almost half of the young women surveyed using cloth at some point during their periods.

Figure 1 : The Percentage of Women Aged 15–24 Years Using Hygienic Methods of Menstrual Protection in Relation to the Number of Years of Schooling

Source: National Family Health Survey (Round 4 and 5)

Looking at the NFHS data on the indicator of years of schooling, we can clearly see a direct relationship between the usage of hygiene methods for menstrual protection and the

of years of schooling. As the person's schooling years increase, so does the likelihood of using hygiene methods (Figure 1). Conversely, the percentage of young women using unhygienic menstrual protection practices such as using unhygienic cloth rags, decreases with the increase in the number of years of schooling. The most significant observation is the marked improvement over time, from the fourth round (2015–16) to the fifth round (2019–21) across all levels of education. We can observe from Figure 1 that the difference is higher among those with no schooling at all, in comparison to all the remaining educational levels, with a 23.6% difference. This shows that awareness is a key factor, and it can be effectively raised through the provision of education.

Social characteristics are another indicator to gauge menstrual health in general and the usage of menstrual protection in particular. The data has shown an improved statistical observation of hygienic menstrual practices with the advancement of time. Categorically speaking, the Scheduled Tribes have shown a better improvement across the surveys in comparison with the Other Backward Classes, a jump of almost 15% and 12%, respectively (NFHS 5th Round). The highest percentage in the usage of hygienic products was shown by the Other or the General category. On the other hand, the highest percentage of the usage of unhygienic methods such as clothes was seen among the members of Scheduled Tribes at 60.8% in 2019–21 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Percentage of Women Aged 15–24 Years Using Cloth for Menstrual Protection across Social Categories

Source: National Family Health Survey (Round 4 and 5)

We have also observed a relationship between menstrual hygiene practices and the differences in wealth holdings. To carry out this analysis, we looked at the wealth quintile indicator from the NFHS data sets. As Figure 3 shows, there is a directly proportional relationship between the percentage of young women using hygienic methods of menstrual protection and the wealth quintile; that is, the use of hygienic methods is more

periods as wealth increases. The gap between the two rounds of surveys is larger for the poorest than for the richest, 32.5% and 6%, respectively. Similarly, Figure 4 shows a negative relationship between the percentage of young women using clothes for menstrual protection and the wealth quintile. Even though the usage of clothes reduces significantly as wealth increases, we cannot claim that there is an absolute absence of unhygienic practices of menstrual protection among the richest section. Almost 23% of the highest wealth-holding section were seen using cloth for menstrual protection in the year 2021 (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Percentage of Women Aged 15–24 Years Using Hygienic Methods of Menstrual Protection across Wealth Quintiles

Source: National Family Health Survey (Round 4 and 5)

Figure 4: Percentage of Women Aged 15–24 Years Using Clothes for Menstrual Protection across Wealth Quintiles

Source: National Family Health Survey (Round 4 and 5)

Analysing the data state-wise, 16 states and UTs have more than 90% of young women using hygienic methods. Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, and Meghalaya have the lowest use of hygienic methods, at 59.2%, 60.9%, and 65.3%, respectively. On the other hand, Tamil Nadu has the highest percentage of young women using hygienic methods at 98.4% (Figure 5). Orissa observed the highest improvement in the use of hygienic products at 34%, followed by Rajasthan and West Bengal between 2015–16 and 2019–21 (Chawla, 2022).

Certain data limitations with NFHS are that the data captures only young women's access to menstrual products. There is no information available for the adult women group of 25–49 years and non-binary individuals and transgenders who also experience menstruation.

Figure 5: State-wise Percentage of Women Aged 15–24 Years Using Hygienic Methods of Menstrual Protection in 2019–21

Source: National Family Health Survey (Round 5)

3. Challenges with Maintaining Menstrual Hygiene and Health

Period poverty is defined as the lack of access to period products, menstrual health education and Water, Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) facilities. Practices related to hygiene during menstruation are significantly important, as they have health implications, leading to a higher susceptibility to reproductive tract infections (RTI). Furthermore, the absence of proper menstrual hygiene products heightens the risk of reproductive and urinary tract infections. Hence, prioritising and ensuring proper hygiene practices during menstruation significantly impacts the immediate health and well-being of individuals.

Accessibility to affordable hygienic menstrual absorbents is crucial for healthy menstrual management practices. Despite various initiatives, achieving universal availability and accessibility of clean absorbents remains challenging in India. As observed through the NFHS data, 49.3% of young women still rely on using old cloth, often due to financial constraints or lack of awareness. Disposable sanitary pads, though providing safe menstrual hygiene, are costly, particularly for low-income households and also pose a huge environmental burden. While compostable disposables offer an eco-friendly option, they are limited in availability and expensive. Also, reusable menstrual products, although budget-friendly and eco-friendly, require the support of WASH infrastructure and a stigma-free environment in order to be used properly. Addressing these challenges requires efforts to increase affordability and access to both reusable and disposable menstrual absorbents, ensuring comprehensive menstrual health management for all menstruating individuals.

For menstruating individuals, a secure water supply and clean, functional, private toilet facilities are needed to handle menstruation. Having these facilities can be the determining factor for menstruating students continuing education or dropping out. Households with access to basic sanitation facilities vary across the country. The NFHS 2019–21 data shows that Bihar, Jharkhand, and Orissa have the lowest percentages in terms of people accessing basic sanitation facilities, with 49.4%, 56.7%, and 60.5%, respectively, while Kerala has the highest, with 98.7%. It can be inferred from this data that menstruating individuals in states with low availability of basic sanitation facilities will face bigger challenges in menstrual health management.

3.1 Intersections of Menstrual Health and Hygiene

Cultural Taboos and Stigmas: Menstrual Hygiene Management remains a taboo topic in India, leaving individuals ill-prepared as they enter puberty due to knowledge gaps and misconceptions. Despite its biological nature, menstruation is covered in secrecy and myths in many cultures, leading to significant social and cultural taboos. Across the country, menstruation is often viewed as dirty and impure, a belief rooted in ancient texts which restricts women from participating in everyday activities and religious practices during their periods. Such myths extend to dietary restrictions, like avoiding sour foods and misconceptions about hygiene and contamination. The stigma and lack of education

around menstruation negatively impacts the lives of many, causing emotional distress, discontinuing of education, , and health issues due to inadequate menstrual hygiene practices. Cultural beliefs associating menstruation with impurity and pollution further magnify these challenges, leading to a widespread sense of shame and exclusion (Garg & Anand, 2015).

In Uttar Pradesh, a study by McCammon et al. (2020) revealed that young women who participated in their study were unprepared for menstruation, lacked awareness before menarche, and faced knowledge gaps and misinformation afterwards. The authors noted that menstruation was stigmatised socially and within families, limiting discussion and mobility during menstruation.

Adults, including parents and teachers, are uncomfortable discussing sexuality and menstruation, perpetuating cultural taboos. Even adult women may lack awareness, passing on misconceptions. There is a significant knowledge gap among girls regarding the origins of menstrual blood, and men and boys are even less informed. The societal silence and taboos surrounding menstruation, coupled with the perception that it is solely a women's issue, deter men from engaging with the topic. This poses challenges in accessing necessary resources such as sanitary products, toilets for menstrual management, and managing pre-menstrual syndrome (PMS) symptoms and pain during menstrual cycles.

Furthermore, alongside cultural taboos interwoven with caste perceptions, women have to adhere to myriad customs during menstruation. Cultural practices prevent women from engaging in daily activities, restricting them from touching water or food, participating in religious acts, or entering religious places. The more severe forms of restrictions compel women to stay isolated and avoid social interaction during menstruation. Sociocultural restrictions can restrict proper menstrual health management despite the availability of necessary resources and facilities (MacRae et al., 2019).

Caste: There is also the intersectionality of prevalent social norms, cultural practices, and stigma against menstruation with caste. Prevalent patriarchal and caste-based customs of purity and pollution render menstruating women as impure and untouchable. The idea of women's bodies as “impure and inferior objects” propagates male domination and enables men to continue to retain control over women and their sexuality (Sukumar, 2020, p. 140). In addition, there is the aspect of women belonging to the lower castes, such as Dalits, who face “particular and complex problems—untouchability, caste discrimination, and oppression” that are different from the problems of a menstruating “upper caste” woman who is considered impure and polluting only during her period (Sukumar, 2020, p.141).

The caste angle is also evident in the reality that improper disposal of products affects sanitation workers (often Dalit men), exposing them to dangerous tasks such as unclogging sewers and toilets (Sukumar, 2020).

Livelihood: A sizeable number of women in the country (39.8% in 2022–23) are employed in diverse occupations, making the workplace a significant place for menstrual health management. Around 90% of India's working women are employed in the informal sector (Subhalakshmi, 2020). Employers in the informal sector often lack legal obligations to cater to women's sanitation needs at work. Additionally, women in these roles often lack the power to influence the enforcement of hygiene standards. This situation is particularly challenging for women who are construction workers, whose menstrual hygiene management needs are often overlooked by employers. For women who are self-employed, such as food vendors, access to public sanitation facilities during work hours may be limited. Without a safe space to manage menstruation, women may experience anxiety, reduced productivity and health issues. Some women may even miss workdays altogether, impacting their income and that of their employers (Sommer et al., 2016).

What was and is happening in Beed, Maharashtra, is an example of the extent to which women's reproductive health suffers due to the lack of sanitation and hygiene facilities, the nature of work, and intense pressure from the employer to attain certain targets. A high incidence of hysterectomies in Beed came to light with a study reporting 4,605 hysterectomies conducted between 2016–17 and 2017–19. The Maharashtra State Commission for Women found that 36% of the women sugar cane cutters had undergone a hysterectomy. One of the reasons for getting a hysterectomy was to stop menstruation during the cane-cutting season, assuming that it would make them more productive if they did not face any menstruation pain. However, post-surgery, it was seen that most women faced backaches, weakness, and other conditions, reducing their quality of life, productivity, and income (Shulka & Kulkarni, 2019).

The low share of women's participation in the country's workforce makes it imperative for policymakers to ensure that women are not compelled to leave their jobs due to inadequate sanitary facilities and a supportive environment in their workplaces. Women in the informal economy are particularly vulnerable to job losses, and the high number of women in this sector necessitates “period-friendly workplaces” to ensure their continued employment.

Sexual and Reproductive Health: Sexual and reproductive health (SRH) encompasses physical, emotional, mental, and social well-being concerning sexuality and reproduction. It is about more than just being free from illness or issues. Menstrual health is a crucial part of SRH because menstruation and the menstrual cycle affect key reproductive experiences throughout life, both physically and socially (Wilson et al., 2021). However, MHM programs do not align well with or often do not cover the broader areas of SRH.

In India, MHM efforts mainly target adolescents, emphasising that good practices and understanding during puberty carry over into adulthood. However, adult women need

knowledge about how fertility and menstrual cycles link and how contraceptives can affect cycles. Similarly, older women must understand changes during menopause, like irregular bleeding or hormonal shifts, which are often overlooked and discussed less openly than other SRH issues. It is, therefore, important to understand the different stages of the reproductive cycle to prepare for and manage the symptoms.

Therefore, it is crucial to integrate menstrual health and hygiene into broader sexual and reproductive health discussions.

Nutrition: Poor nutrition, high Body Mass Index (BMI), un-nutritious food consumption, meal skipping during menses, female dieting, and low physical activity contribute to menstrual problems. Foods that lack vital micronutrients like vitamin B6, calcium, magnesium, and potassium worsen premenstrual symptoms and irregular periods. Studies link intake of a low-nutritious diet with issues such as abnormal flow, dysmenorrhea, and PMS. Addressing these dietary habits is critical for enhancing menstrual health, especially in India, where a significant section of women and girls aged 15–49 years (57%, according to NFHS-5) are anaemic (Government of India, 2022).

Gender-Based Violence: The linkage between gender-based violence and menstruation has been reported in some countries. Married women in Uganda have reported instances of domestic violence by their husbands when they attempt to manage their periods by cutting blankets (CARE International in Uganda, 2018). In certain circumstances, young girls in Nigeria, lacking access to affordable menstrual products, have been forced into trading sex to obtain these necessities, increasing the risk of getting sexually transmitted diseases and experiencing gender-based violence (Odey et al., 2021). The underlying cause is period poverty and the lack of WASH infrastructure, which forces women to engage in activities that make them vulnerable. So, there is a need to explore and research more on the linkage of how the lack of menstrual health and hygiene facilities in India perpetuates gender-based violence.

Education: The intersection of gender equality, especially in education, and menstrual health management is particularly significant. As per the National Sample Survey, 2017–18, the literacy rate of women in rural areas is 65% compared to 81.5%, which translates to a 16.5% gender gap in rural areas compared to 14.4% in urban areas. Ensuring that girls continue to stay in school and attain their full potential is especially important since the gender gap in literacy rates remains high, especially in rural areas.

School can play a great role in demystifying the stigmas and taboos related to menstrual health and hygiene. Additionally, adequate facilities and a sensitive environment must ensure that there are no barriers to girls' education. By ensuring comprehensive menstrual education in the curriculum, providing access to sanitary pads, and providing a safe environment, schools can be game changers in breaking the stigmas around menstruation and promoting better health outcomes for girls (Smile Foundation, 2023).

Unhealthy menstrual health practices would also lead to girls losing access to education. The Hindu reported that 60% of adolescent girls skipped school while on their periods (Hindu, 2018). Absenteeism among school girls due to menstruation ranged from 10% to 40% (Muthusamy Sivakami et al., 2019; Vashisht et al., 2018). In addition to absenteeism, menstruation affects the quality of school time, with surveys revealing that many girls report their inability to concentrate in school, apart from experiencing pain (Muthusamy Sivakami et al., 2019).

3.2 Neglected Demographics and Scenarios

Disaster Situations: Climate change is causing increasingly frequent and more intense disaster events across the world, particularly in India. These events have caused loss of lives and massive damage to homes and livelihoods. In 2023, all the states and union territories of the country experienced extreme weather events on 235 days of the first nine months of the year (Down to Earth, 2023).

Disasters or emergency situations present significant challenges for managing personal and menstrual hygiene, elevating the risk of various health issues that can jeopardise women's lives. Disasters, therefore, amplify existing gender inequalities, disproportionately affecting women and girls, whose menstrual hygiene needs are frequently neglected by both communities and government responses (Mondal, 2020).

India faces numerous humanitarian crises that deeply impact its diverse population. The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 highlighted India's vulnerability to disasters, revealing the compounded challenges communities face and emphasising the link between socioeconomic disparities and emergency susceptibility (UNFPA & WaterAid India, 2021).

Women and girls in low-resource settings face numerous obstacles in managing menstruation due to deeply ingrained sociocultural norms, limited access to information and support services, unreliable access to products, and inadequate sanitation facilities. These challenges are magnified during emergencies, where the loss of privacy, safety, and essential services further complicates menstrual management (UNFPA & WaterAid India, 2021).

A pan-India study was conducted by the JSS Institute of Economic Research, Dharwad, to understand the challenges of menstrual health and hygiene practices among adolescent girls in climate-vulnerable areas. The research observes various scenarios and situations such as floods, cyclones, drought, and snowfall. As per the study, overall, 46% of interviewed girls expressed that they had to go through difficult situations during climate extremes, with varying experiences across states and rural and urban residents. Almost

half of the girls mentioned that they faced problems relating to getting water. The ways of managing were methods like boiling water for drinking (21.5%) to ensure cleanliness and not taking a bath (14%), among other ways. Almost a third of the respondents in flood/cyclone-affected areas expressed that they had to face problems relating to washing menstrual cloth or to disposing of sanitary napkins. Similarly, bathing during climate disasters was another issue addressed by the study. In the flood/cyclone-affected areas, 15.9% expressed unavailability of water to bathe, and 18.8% expressed privacy concerns. Climatic disasters usually make the residents of that area move away from their homes and stay in camps/tents.

Among the interviewees who had to move to camps/tents, 40% mentioned that they had no place to change their pads, and 28.4% expressed concerns about lack of privacy and security. Overall, the impact of crises and their accompanying circumstances were felt higher in rural areas than in urban areas (Hallad et al., 2023).

Several studies have identified some of the main barriers impacting menstrual hygiene practices for women during recurrent disasters and displacement. First, inadequate housing emerged as a significant challenge. Following disasters, women often had to live in damaged homes, tents, or shelters with no private space to manage menstrual hygiene. These overcrowded and non-weatherproof shelters lacked essential facilities such as washrooms, bathing areas, and water supply. As a result, women had to travel to rivers to wash their menstrual clothes, often drying them discreetly in plastic bags or under trees. Privacy and safety concerns were prevalent, with women feeling uncomfortable and insecure using communal washrooms or open fields. Even when private washrooms are available, they often lack essential features like doors, locks, and lighting, making them inadequate for managing menstruation. These conditions not only complicate menstrual hygiene management but also increase the risk of exposure to violence and exploitation, particularly at night when women and girls seek private spaces to address their sanitary needs (Hirani, 2024; Schmitt et al., 2017).

Second, inadequate infrastructure and humanitarian help posed another critical barrier. Humanitarian aid primarily focused on basic needs like food and shelter, neglecting the provision of menstrual supplies and safe spaces in disaster-relief camps. Women had to resort to using children's clothes as menstrual pads and faced difficulties in maintaining hygiene due to the absence of water and washing facilities. The situation is further worsened by severe weather conditions, with no private bathing facilities available within a reasonable distance, making it even more challenging to manage menstrual hygiene.

The third barrier is the absence of a waste disposal system. Without proper waste disposal facilities, women were forced to bury or burn their menstrual clothes discreetly. This improper disposal can lead to multiple health concerns due to the accumulation of waste

and flies, further complicating the already dire conditions imposed by the crises. (Hirani, 2024; Schmitt et al., 2017).

Person with Disabilities (PwD) : Managing menstruation in a dignified and healthy way can present unique challenges for individuals with disabilities. A 2019 systematic review of menstrual hygiene management requirements, barriers, and strategies for persons with disabilities revealed that menstruation challenges often lead to shame for these individuals, resulting in social isolation and, in extreme cases, forced sterilisation (UNICEF, 2020). The lack of proper water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) facilities in communities, schools, healthcare facilities, and public places add to the numerous barriers that prevent girls and women with disabilities from fully participating in social and economic life. There is also a common misconception that girls with disabilities do not menstruate, highlighting the need for education to dispel myths about menstruation and disability (UNICEF, 2020). While inclusive education and employment initiatives are underway, the menstrual health needs of PwDs are frequently overlooked and inadequately addressed, leading to adverse health outcomes and diminished well-being (WaterAid India & UNFPA, 2022).

PwDs often face challenges in managing menstrual health and hygiene due to the triple burden of disability, gender, and sociocultural aspects of menstruation. Access barriers such as inaccessible water, sanitation, and hygiene intensify challenges. Lack of disability-inclusive menstrual health interventions and limited awareness and support contribute to difficulties in managing menstrual health and hygiene effectively. Hence, despite the increased global and national focus on menstrual health and hygiene, the discourse around the intersection of menstruation and disability remains limited. This gap calls for urgent attention and action (WaterAid India & UNFPA, 2022).

Prisoners: The availability of proper menstrual health management facilities for women prisoners is another area of significant concern. According to Prison Statistics in India, in 2022, there were 23,722 women prisoners, with only 10.3% (4,258) housed in dedicated women-only jails. The majority are kept in women's sections within male prisons. Around 75% of these women are aged between 18 and 50, while 19.5% are over 50.

Although a sizable number of regular menstruators are in prisons, they often lack basic amenities such as clean toilets, sufficient dustbins, and proper disposal facilities for sanitary napkins (Harad, 2023). A report by the Commonwealth Human Rights Initiative on Haryana's prisons found that although most jails provide sanitary napkins, some women were unaware of this service or had to buy pads from the canteen. In cases where pads were unavailable, women resorted to using cloth or rags. Additionally, female

prisoners sometimes felt uncomfortable being checked by male doctors, especially when discussing reproductive or menstrual health issues.

Similarly, a study conducted in a Maharashtra prison in June 2023 revealed inadequate water, sanitation, and hygiene facilities for women. Limited water supply forced them to store water, occupying space in the few toilets available. Approximately 50 women shared just two toilets, causing issues with hygiene, including the insufficient supply and poor quality of sanitary napkins. This led to discomfort, skin irritations, and infections among women (Gupta & Sivakami, 2024).

A report by the Common Health Rights Initiative, "Periods in Prisons," checks the MHM standards and practices of 11 women's prisons across seven states in India. The report highlights how prisons follow different standards for the provision of menstrual products. This is because the Model Prison Manual specifies that products have to be made available to women prisoners, but it does not specify the quantity of products that women can access and leaving room for possible misuse or confusion regarding the provision. Hence, there is a need for more research to understand the conditions of MHM in prisons and make suitable changes and policies.

4. Menstrual Waste Management

Managing menstrual waste is crucial for ensuring the well-being of menstruating individuals. When we talk about menstrual waste, we refer to the blood and tissues, and used menstrual products like cloth pads, disposable sanitary napkins, cups, and other absorbent materials (WaterAid India, 2019). In India alone, approximately 36% of women of reproductive age use sanitary napkins, resulting in a staggering 100 crores of used pads every month. Properly managing this waste involves safely disposing of and treating these used products to prevent harm to both individuals handling the waste and the environment (The Economic Times, 2023).

To put things into perspective, India has around 33.6 crore menstruating women, with about 121 million of them using disposable sanitary napkins. Considering an average usage of eight napkins per cycle, this adds up to a staggering 12.3 billion disposable sanitary napkins annually in India alone. Sadly, most of these products are not biodegradable or compostable, worsening the concerns (Malaviya, 2018). Additionally, the belief that menstrual blood is impure and must be concealed or discreetly disposed of compels menstruating individuals to hide menstrual blood from pads before disposal. Women often wrap these pads in newspapers or plastic bags, sometimes even rinsing off the blood beforehand. These practices increase the use of resources required for disposal and contribute to environmental strain. It has been projected that by 2030 if all discarded products are washed and wrapped, an additional 1,800 million tons of plastic and water will be used. The culture of silence and shame surrounding menstruation, particularly pronounced in developing nations, leads to disposal methods that bear significant environmental and social ramifications for individuals involved in waste management (Lopez, 2021).

Below, we explore the risk factors associated with poor menstrual waste management, categorised into the environmental impact of improper waste management and the related health implications and dignity concerns.

Environmental Risks: In many rural and urban areas across India, there is a glaring absence of regular waste collection systems. This leads to the improper disposal of used menstrual products such as cloth pads and sanitary napkins; these often end up in open fields, water bodies like ponds, lakes, rivers, and streams, or are buried or burned openly. Unfortunately, many of these sanitary pads contain non-biodegradable materials like cellulose, super absorbent polymers (SAP), plastic coverings, and adhesives, which persist in the environment, polluting soil and water sources (WaterAid India, 2019).

The scarcity of proper incineration facilities intensifies this waste crisis. While some institutions like schools, airports, and malls, have them, many need proper certification to ensure they meet emission standards set by the Central Pollution Control Board. Additionally, low-cost incinerators often operate at insufficiently high temperatures and lack adequate mechanisms to control the release of these toxic emissions, making them potential health hazards for individuals in nearby communities (Malaviya, 2018).

Health and Dignity at Risk: When menstruators lack proper disposal facilities, they may resort to using pads for longer periods than recommended, leading to unhygienic practices and an increased risk of infections (WaterAid India, 2019). Furthermore, a significant amount of these sanitary products end up in landfills, where waste pickers are compelled to sift through them manually. This exposes them to potential diseases, especially as non-biodegradable products contaminate water sources or are inadequately disposed of through burning. Waste pickers often handle discarded products without protective gear, worsening health risks. Moreover, societal taboos surrounding menstruation can further deter waste pickers from engaging with menstrual waste and supporting proper waste management initiatives (Malaviya, 2018; The Economic Times, 2023).

A report from the Times of India highlighted the issue of improper disposal, where pads and menstrual products are casually discarded along with dry waste without proper wrapping. This places the burden on garbage collectors and waste personnel, who must separate these items manually to earn a living. This negligence fails to consider the humanity of those who handle the waste, neglecting their well-being and dignity in the process (The Economic Times, 2023).

5. India's Stance on Menstrual Health and Hygiene

Menstrual health emerged as a notable public health issue in India, which was previously overlooked by governments, NGOs, and businesses until the early 2000s. Since then, India has made creditable steps in prioritising the well-being and hygiene of women and girls during menstruation.

From 2005 to 2010, the government included menstrual health and hygiene (MHH) in the responsibilities of Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs) as part of the National Rural Health Mission. In 2010, India started the Menstrual Hygiene Scheme (MHS) to give sanitary napkins to young girls. The Rashtriya Kishor Swasthya Karyakram program, under the Reproductive, Maternal, Newborn, Child, and Adolescent Health scheme, increased awareness of and access to sanitary pads. In 2011, the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare issued guidelines for menstrual hygiene management; additional instructions came from the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation in 2015. In 2012, the Nirmal Bharat Yatra, a flagship sanitation program that included MHH, was launched. Concurrently, other similar programs under the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan also began to be implemented, including some focused on promoting the use of sanitary napkin vending machines and incinerators for safe disposal. These efforts increased India's menstrual product usage from 15% of menstruating women in 2010 to 57% in 2015–16, and further to 78% in 2019–21 (Babbar & Ojha, 2023).

The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare has also implemented the “Scheme for Promotion of Menstrual Hygiene,” which aims to enhance menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls aged 10–19 years. Funds were allocated based on proposals from States and Union Territories in their Programme Implementation Plan (PIP) under the National Health Mission. The scheme's key objectives include raising awareness about menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls, improving access to and usage of high-quality sanitary napkins, and ensuring the safe disposal of napkins in an environmentally friendly manner.

Also, as part of Pradhan Mantri Bharatiya Janausadhi Pariyojna (PMBJP), a scheme to ensure the accessibility of quality generic medicines at affordable prices, Suvidha oxo-biodegradable sanitary napkins are being sold at Rs.1/pad. This initiative within the scheme was introduced in 2019 and is available for sale in more than 10,607 PMBJP kendras across the country.

Moreover, a joint letter issued in the year 2022 by the Secretary of Department of School Education and Literacy and the Secretary of the Ministry of Jal Shakti advised states to utilise allocated funds for Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM) and disposal of menstrual waste under Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin) Phase-II at the village level, installing or maintaining incinerators in schools with girls from classes VI to XII, and raising awareness about MHM among adolescent girls and in society at large (Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India, 2023b).

5.1 Goonj's Comprehensive Idea for Scale

Goonj, a multi-award-winning social enterprise operating across India, serves as an economic bridge between urban centres and rural communities. Over the past 25 years, it has cultivated a culture of mindful giving, repurposing surplus resources such as clothing and medicines that would otherwise remain unused.

Redefining the Problem

Goonj has successfully reframed the discourse surrounding menstruation, moving beyond the traditional perception of it as solely a “women's issue” and instead placing it within the broader context of human dignity. Central to this repositioning is the recognition of the profound impact of shame and silence on menstruators. By elevating the discourse around “Menstruators Dignity,” Goonj has shed light on the multifaceted dimensions of this issue, amplifying the voices of historically marginalised individuals.

This inclusive approach advocates for comprehensive research to capture the diverse experiences of women across various intersections, including those residing in remote regions, enduring natural disasters, or facing challenging circumstances. Through these efforts, Goonj has underscored the intersectionality of menstruation with other critical aspects of society, such as disability, migration, and climate emergencies.

Through citizen-driven advocacy campaigns among the masses and its annual sector-level dialogue on menstruation, Goonj has facilitated and convened multifaceted voices that were previously overlooked. Furthermore, it has connected stakeholders from civil society organisations, rural and urban communities and other sectors to highlight areas in the policy landscape surrounding Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM) that need attention, playing a pivotal role in broadening the discourse on menstruation and advocating for more holistic approaches to addressing its associated challenges.

Creating a Comprehensive Framework for MHM

In the past 25 years, through its flagship initiative, “Not Just a Piece of Cloth” (NJPC), Goonj has been mainstreaming menstruation as a human issue, emphasising the most marginalised women's voice, dignity, well-being, and choices. It repurposes surplus cloth to produce cloth sanitary pads, organises nationwide “Break the Silence” dialogues, and leads community-led actions on rural women's hyper-local menstrual issues. Goonj's approach focuses on the voices and needs of the most missed-out and marginalised women, including tribal women, sex workers, the LGBTQ community, disabled women and others. By evolving a “4 A's approach—Awareness, Affordability, Access, and Action—the Goonj model around menstrual well-being of menstruators in India takes a comprehensive socio, ecological, economic, and place-based approach to address diverse menstruation-related challenges faced by menstruators across the diversity of India.

A Cloth Pad Made from the Masses for the Masses

Goonj's innovation also lies in establishing reusable cloth pads as a viable product option and making a connection between India's surplus urban cotton cloth and the challenge of access and affordability for the most marginalised rural women. Goonj's Cloth Sanitary Pad (called MY Pad), made from India's pre- and post-consumer urban surplus cotton and semi-cotton cloth, is an innovative idea that has been increasing access to cotton/semi-cotton reusable sanitary pads to rural women since 2005 (McLaren & Padhee, 2021).

Goonj collects urban pre- and post-consumer cotton cloth from urban India at scale through close collaborations with different urban entities: individuals, schools, colleges, Resident Welfare Associations, corporations, etc. It has been making millions of cloth pads by putting this cloth through a simple process of sorting cotton/semi-cotton cloth and then a washing, drying, and basic stitching process. It reaches these pads to rural women across India through a wide network of rural partnerships with grassroots organisations, panchayats, schools, self-help groups, etc. In rural India, Goonj uses these cloth pads as a nudge to mobilise women for “Break the Silence” conversations for better menstrual hygiene awareness, and it motivates these women to take action on their weak hyper-local WASH infrastructure (Gopakumar, 2022).

While this innovation emerged in-house from Goonj's last two decades of work on surplus material (especially cloth), it connects back to the argument that innovation is not only dependent on epochs but also on the particularities of specific countries or regions (Freeman & Perez, 1988). Goonj's work in the last two decades coincides with India's economic liberalisation and consumption boom, as well as India's unique position as the world's biggest cotton producer. Through this process and value chain innovation (Lundvall, B.Å., et al. 2011, p.58), Goonj adopted a new insourcing of cotton cloth, which is resource-saving and beneficial to the environment while it also moved the henceforth unconnected textile surplus to a new category of sanitary pad making. Most pad-making firms make cloth pads from new cloth, impacting the affordability of these products for most rural women. This, in turn, weakens the sustainability of these pads (made from new cloth) as they trigger more production of cotton cloth, leading to more natural resource consumption. Sourcing of cloth as raw material from urban surplus aligns with the "limits to growth model" argument (Meadows, D. et al., 2004) for sustainable development as it extends the life of the cloth already present in the system. This innovative approach aligns with global sustainability models, extending the life of surplus cloth and promoting resource conservation.

Surfacing Intersectional Elements

According to the 2011 Census, 55% of rural households do not have any enclosed bathing space within the premises, and this proportion rises to an alarming high of 95% in poorer pockets of India. Women have no option, then, but to bathe fully clothed in nearby ponds, wells, hand pumps, or streams. Apart from hygiene, this compromises their dignity as well. Goonj's menstrual hygiene initiatives also stand out because they intersect with critical issues such as sanitation, nutrition, climate emergencies, cloth waste management, and women's agency and dignity. Its work has surfaced new insights and ideas for the sector, embedding menstrual hygiene in practical ways within the broader context of sanitation and climate resilience.

Building a Strong Interconnection between Menstrual Hygiene and Climate Emergencies

In the face of frequent climate emergencies, Goonj has integrated menstrual well-being into its relief and rehabilitation work with disaster-hit communities. Its MY Pad ATMs, developed in rural India, provide cost-effective access to clean cloth pads during emergencies, addressing the unique challenges faced by women in such situations. In 2018, Goonj pioneered the "MY Pad ATM" initiative in the rural Bundelkhand region, as it recognised the lack of access to affordable menstrual products and poor connectivity in these far-flung areas. Goonj teams repurposed suitcases as MY Pad ATMs to provide awareness, accessibility, and affordability of menstrual hygiene products to women who previously struggled to manage their menstruation safely and with dignity due to poverty. On the one hand, this innovative solution gives new life to materials that would otherwise go to waste, while on the other hand, it directly addresses the critical need for a sustainable solution by offering low-cost sanitary pads (repurposed cloth pads).

Impact, Scale, and Replication

Just in the last nine years, Goonj has reached more than 80 lakh single cloth pads and over 5 lakh undergarments across India (2015–23) to close to 4 lakh women. It has also held more than 11,500 awareness sessions, motivating communities to take up more than 16,000 WASH infrastructure building/repair projects (kitchen gardens, dustbins, water body premises, bathroom/private spaces). In the process, it has converted over 2 lakhs sq. meters of surplus cotton cloth into better pieces of cloth for women's menstrual well-being since 2015.

The Goonj initiative on menstrual well-being across urban and rural India provides valuable insights for policy inputs. Insights include the interconnection between menstrual health, women's dignity, and the recognition of menstrual hygiene as a fundamental human right. This encompasses considerations across physical, psychological, and social dimensions. Additionally, the initiative highlights the importance of menstrual well-being in responding to the climate emergency.

5.2 Upcoming Initiative: The Draft Menstrual Hygiene (MH) Policy

The Ministry of Health & Family Welfare in the year 2023 formulated a draft Menstrual Hygiene Policy (MHP) through consultation with stakeholders. This draft policy aims to provide comprehensive support throughout the menstrual journey, catering to the unique needs of individuals from menarche to menopause, with a particular focus on underserved and vulnerable populations. It seeks to ensure fair access to menstrual hygiene resources and address specific needs, acting as a catalyst for awareness-raising, challenging societal norms, and fostering a culture that normalises menstrual hygiene. The draft MHP's goal is to promote the health, well-being, and empowerment of menstruating individuals (Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India, 2023).

Strengths of the Draft MH Policy

The policy focuses on various groups, including adolescent girls, women, persons with disabilities, ethnic minorities, trans and nonbinary individuals, and other vulnerable populations. This broad inclusivity ensures that no subgroup is overlooked in the efforts to improve menstrual hygiene.

The policy prioritises improving access to safe menstrual hygiene products and aims to reduce the financial burden of menstruation, especially for those in low-income communities. Initiatives such as the Menstrual Hygiene Scheme and the promotion of innovative techniques for affordability enhance accessibility.

Additionally, the draft policy focuses on comprehensive menstrual hygiene education, which is crucial for preventing stigma and debunking myths associated with menstruation. By integrating this education into school curricula and conducting awareness campaigns, the policy aims to promote a better understanding of menstrual health.

Provision of clean, private, and well-maintained toilets, washing facilities, and disposal systems is essential for enabling individuals to manage their menstrual hygiene safely and with dignity. This aspect is also addressed to support menstrual hygiene management effectively.

Moreover, the policy emphasises collaboration between various stakeholders, including various government departments (such as Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Departments of Health-State/UTs, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Ministry of Women and Child Development, Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Ministry of Chemicals & Fertilisers, Ministry of Rural Development/Urban Development, Pollution Control Boards/Bodies), NGOs, civil society, academia, and the private sector. This multi-stakeholder approach leverages resources, expertise, and innovative solutions to address menstrual hygiene challenges comprehensively.

Furthermore, the policy advocates for the development and implementation of quality standards and regulatory frameworks for menstrual hygiene products. Clear labelling requirements and monitoring mechanisms ensure consumer safety and product effectiveness, promoting confidence in the products available in the market.

The MH policy also encourages research institutes and academia to contribute to evidence-based policymaking and promote innovation in menstrual hygiene management, ensuring that policies remain up to date with emerging scientific knowledge and technological advancements.

Menstrual hygiene principles are integrated into existing health, education, sanitation, gender, and environment programs to ensure a holistic approach to address menstrual hygiene management. This integration helps in leveraging existing infrastructure and resources across different sectors to maximise impact.

Overall, the policy demonstrates a comprehensive approach to menstrual hygiene management, addressing not only access to products but also education, infrastructure, regulatory standards, research, and collaboration. Finally, the emphasis on inclusive relief strategies during emergencies highlights the importance of addressing MHM in crisis situations.

Roadblocks

Implementing a menstrual health policy in a populous country like India indeed faces numerous hurdles. While the policy outlines various initiatives, the actual implementation and monitoring of these strategies may face challenges, especially at the grassroots level. While promoting open discussions on menstruation is essential, cultural sensitivities and diverse societal norms need to be considered to ensure the effectiveness of awareness campaigns.

Additionally, the policy does not explicitly address the allocation of resources needed to support the proposed interventions, which could impact the feasibility of implementation. The proposed initiatives need to ensure long-term sustainability, especially in terms of funding and stakeholder engagement. The policy should, therefore, delineate clear goals, both short-term and long-term, to ensure its effectiveness over time.

Recognising the vital link between health and menstruation is essential for shaping effective policies. Central to this approach is understanding the critical role of nutrition in menstrual health. Insufficient awareness of a balanced diet can lead to malnutrition and hormonal imbalances, significantly impacting menstrual well-being. Thus, the draft policy on menstrual hygiene should prioritise inclusion of key nutrients, highlighting their importance in supporting menstrual health (UNESCO Office, New Delhi, 2023).

Expanding menstrual health education to increase sexual and fertility awareness is also necessary. Understanding the menstrual cycle's reproductive role can significantly enhance sexual and reproductive health (SRH) outcomes. Combining menstrual health with comprehensive sexual education equips menstruators with the necessary tools to manage their reproductive health across various life stages, from puberty through family planning to menopause (USAID GlobalWaters, 2022).

By intertwining nutrition education with menstrual health initiatives and expanding sexual education to include menstrual health, the menstrual draft policy can effectively address individuals' multifaceted needs.

Moreover, the draft menstrual hygiene policy does not provide specifics on how it will assist the targeted demographic within prison facilities. Without a clear plan for implementation and support mechanisms tailored to the unique challenges faced by incarcerated individuals, the policy's effectiveness in addressing menstrual hygiene needs remains unclear. Also, the Ministry of Home Affairs, which is responsible for prisons, is not incorporated into the roles of the stakeholders.

Furthermore, given that the draft menstrual hygiene policy involves multiple government ministries and their personnel, it should consider incorporating the Ministry of Labour & Employment. This addition would ensure supervision of the rights and dignity of employees working at the grassroots level, encouraging a comprehensive approach to support all individuals affected by the policy.

Points Raised by the Panellists during the Menstruation Dialogue 2024

1. **Inclusive Language:** Emphasising the use of inclusive language, such as “menstruators,” acknowledges that menstruation affects individuals of all genders.
2. **Collective Responsibility:** Addressing menstrual health issues is a collective responsibility that transcends gender boundaries and requires everyone's involvement.
3. **Engagement with Patriarchy:** Highlighting that combating patriarchy and its norms, like menstruation itself, requires continual engagement rather than a one-time solution.
4. **Destigmatisation through Dialogue:** Addressing cultural taboos surrounding menstruation through open dialogue to support and destigmatise this natural bodily function.
5. **Visibility of Menstrual Products:** Displaying menstrual products prominently in public areas and workspaces to normalise and destigmatise this natural process.
6. **Amplifying Marginalised Voices:** Harnessing the potential of collective action in menstrual health advocacy by amplifying marginalised voices and challenging societal norms.
7. **Comprehensive Data Collection:** Stressing the importance of collecting comprehensive data on menstruation and menopause to understand the scope of these issues.
8. **Neglect in Public Healthcare:** Despite India's extensive public healthcare network, menstrual health remains neglected, which is evident by insufficient research, counselling services, and products specifically addressing the physical and emotional challenges menstruators face.
9. **Interdisciplinary Research:** Advocating for interdisciplinary research integrating medical, social, and cultural perspectives to address menstrual health challenges comprehensively.
10. **Role of Internet Literacy:** Acknowledging that internet literacy can empower women to challenge social norms and negotiate conventions related to menstruation.
11. **Addressing Overlooked Sections:** Including overlooked groups such as sex workers, women prisoners, and those in disaster-stricken situations in menstrual health initiatives.
12. **Environmental Impact:** Advocating for biodegradable measures in menstrual waste disposal to mitigate environmental impact.
13. **Comprehensive Policy Needs:** Emphasising the necessity for menstrual health policies that extend beyond holidays and leaves to address the needs of women in manual labour, agriculture, rural settings, schools, universities, and domestic labour.
14. **Recognising the intersectionality of menstrual health and hygiene with sexual reproductive health and gender-based violence.**
15. **Personal Responsibility for Change:** True change begins with individuals challenging their own conditioned beliefs and behaviours. Breaking harmful cultural norms within oneself is imperative to ensuring meaningful societal change.

6. International Perspectives

Menstrual health policies have gained significant traction globally, with various countries implementing measures to ensure accessibility, affordability, and support for menstrual health and hygiene. Here is an overview of some countries with established menstrual health policies.

United Kingdom: At the national level, the United Kingdom established a Period Poverty Taskforce to tackle the escalating problem of period poverty. Chaired by the Minister for Women & Equalities, this task force collaborates with key stakeholders, including organisations like Plan International and Procter & Gamble, to develop and implement initiatives aimed at comprehensively addressing period poverty.

The Period Poverty Taskforce exemplifies a coordinated approach to combating period poverty, leveraging partnerships between government agencies, non-profit organisations, and private sector entities. By pooling resources and expertise, the task force endeavours to implement sustainable solutions that address the root causes of period poverty and promote menstrual health and well-being for all individuals. This collaborative effort not only demonstrates the shared commitment of various stakeholders but also instils a sense of collective responsibility in addressing this global issue.

Furthermore, charitable organisations such as Bloody Good Period have played a pivotal role in addressing period poverty by distributing menstrual products to vulnerable groups. These organisations, in collaboration with the government, work tirelessly to ensure that individuals facing financial hardship, including those accessing food banks, community support groups, asylum seekers, and homeless shelters, have access to essential menstrual products. Their efforts are a testament to the power of community-driven initiatives in complementing government policies and initiatives. By mobilising resources and volunteers, these organisations extend support to marginalised communities and contribute to a collective effort to combat period poverty and promote menstrual equity.

Scotland: In November 2020, Scotland took a significant step forward in addressing period poverty by enacting The Period Products (Free Provision) (Scotland) Act. This groundbreaking legislation mandates the free provision of menstrual products to all menstruating individuals, ensuring accessibility to essential hygiene products. The Act encompasses a wide range of menstrual products, including disposable pads, tampons, and reusable items like menstrual cups, acknowledging individuals' diverse needs and preferences.

This legislation is a crucial response to the pervasive issue of period poverty, which refers to the inability to afford or access menstrual products due to financial constraints. By making these products freely available, Scotland aims to alleviate the burden of individuals who struggle to afford basic hygiene necessities, thereby promoting menstrual equity and dignity for all. This policy not only addresses a pressing issue but also empowers individuals, giving them the freedom to focus on their lives and aspirations without the worry of period poverty.

Moreover, in October 2023, National Health Service (NHS) Scotland took further steps to support individuals experiencing menopause and menstrual health issues with the launch of the Menopause and Menstrual Health Workplace Policy. This policy underscores the importance of addressing menstrual health concerns in the workplace and provides guidelines for employers to support employees effectively. It includes resources such as guides for line managers and recommendations for workplace adjustments to accommodate the needs of individuals experiencing menopause or menstrual health challenges.

The establishment of the Menopause and Menstrual Health Workplace Policy reflects a growing recognition of the impact of menstrual health on workplace well-being and productivity. By fostering a supportive and inclusive work environment, NHS Scotland aims to enhance the overall health and welfare of its employees while promoting awareness and understanding of menopause and menstrual health issues. This policy not only addresses a health issue but also promotes gender equality and workplace productivity. When employees are supported in managing their menstrual health, they are more likely to be productive and engaged, leading to a more inclusive and productive workplace.

New Zealand: New Zealand's systemic action against period poverty marks a significant step forward in addressing a pervasive issue that disproportionately affects schoolgirls. The provision of free sanitary supplies not only tackles the immediate challenge of accessing menstrual products but also underscores the broader commitment to ensuring uninterrupted education for all students, regardless of socioeconomic background.

The initiative recognises that period poverty not only poses a financial barrier but also impacts educational outcomes and overall well-being. By making organic pads and tampons freely available in schools, the government acknowledges the need for safe and sustainable menstrual products while also alleviating the burden on students and their families. This policy has the potential to [reduce the environmental impact of menstrual products], as organic and reusable products are often more environmentally friendly than their conventional counterparts.

Former Prime Minister Jacinda Ardern's announcement of a nationwide initiative to provide menstrual products in all schools for three years demonstrates political leadership and a commitment to equity in education. By emphasizing the importance of equal access to education, regardless of period-related challenges, Ardern highlights the fundamental principle that no student should face barriers to learning due to their gender or economic circumstances.

This multi-faceted approach addresses both the immediate needs of students and the systemic issues underlying period poverty. By providing free sanitary supplies and promoting initiatives like organic menstrual products in schools, New Zealand aims to create an environment where all students can focus on their education without worrying about access to essential hygiene products. Additionally, by implementing a nationwide initiative, the government signals a long-term commitment to tackling period poverty and promoting gender equality in education. This societal progress not only improves the lives of individuals but also paves the way for a more equitable and inclusive future.

United States of America: The Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security Act (CARES) Act, signed into law in March 2020, introduced several important provisions regarding menstrual products and over-the-counter (OTC) medications, particularly for period pain relief. The CARES Act expanded the eligibility of menstrual products under Flexible Spending Accounts (FSAs) and Health Savings Accounts (HSAs). FSAs and HSAs are tax-advantaged accounts that allow individuals to set aside pre-tax money to cover qualified medical expenses. Before this Act, menstrual products were only sometimes considered eligible expenses under these accounts, which created a financial burden for individuals who rely on these products. By expanding eligibility, the CARES Act acknowledges menstrual products as essential items for personal health and hygiene, ensuring that individuals have greater flexibility in accessing and affording these necessary products. This policy change reflects a broader recognition of menstrual equity issues and aims to alleviate financial barriers to menstrual care.

Another significant provision of the CARES Act is the allowance of over-the-counter (OTC) painkillers for period pain to be available without prescriptions. Menstrual discomfort, including cramps and pain, is a common experience for many individuals during their menstrual cycles. Previously, some OTC pain relief medications for menstrual discomfort required a prescription, which could pose challenges for individuals seeking timely and accessible relief. By removing the prescription requirement, the CARES Act acknowledges the need for accessible pain relief options for individuals experiencing menstrual discomfort. This policy change enables individuals to purchase OTC painkillers for period pain more easily, empowering them to manage their menstrual symptoms effectively without unnecessary barriers.

Spain: Spain's groundbreaking policy to introduce paid menstrual leave marks a significant milestone in addressing women's health and workplace equality. However, this progressive legislation, making Spain the first European country to implement such a measure, has also faced some criticisms. Some argue that it could lead to discrimination against women in the workplace or that it may not include individuals who do not identify as women but still experience painful periods. These are important considerations that highlight the need for ongoing dialogue and refinement of such policies.

The decision to enact this policy reflects a growing recognition of the physical and emotional toll that menstruation can take on women, particularly those who suffer from severe menstrual pain or related conditions like endometriosis. By acknowledging the unique challenges that menstruation presents and affording women the necessary time off to manage their symptoms, Spain is taking a proactive step towards promoting gender equality and supporting women's health in the workplace.

The introduction of paid menstrual leave is rooted in the understanding that menstrual pain can significantly impact a menstruator's ability to perform job duties effectively. Studies have shown that severe menstrual symptoms can lead to decreased productivity, absenteeism, and even workplace discrimination. By providing paid time off specifically for managing menstrual-related issues, Spain's policy aims to alleviate these challenges and create a more supportive and inclusive work environment for women.

Moreover, this legislation sends a powerful message about the importance of reproductive health and well-being in society. By explicitly recognising menstruation as a legitimate health concern deserving of accommodation, Spain is challenging the stigma and taboo surrounding periods and advocating for greater awareness and understanding of women's reproductive health issues.

Learnings for India

The implementation of menstrual health policies across different countries provides valuable lessons and insights for addressing period poverty and promoting menstrual health and hygiene. India can learn several valuable lessons from these international case studies on menstrual health policies. For instance, following the example of National Health Service (NHS) Scotland, India could develop workplace policies that support individuals experiencing menstrual health issues, including menopause. This would promote a more inclusive work environment and contribute to gender equality in the workforce. However, in the Indian context, with a majority of the workforce being in the informal sector, there needs to be ways in which they can also be included as well. Additionally, establishing teams and collaborations between government agencies, non-profit organisations, and private sector entities, as seen in the United Kingdom, can help India develop comprehensive strategies to address period poverty and promote menstrual health.

7. Way Forward and Policy Recommendations

Discussions surrounding menstrual hygiene have gained momentum, addressing crucial elements such as awareness, accessibility, affordability of products, and waste management to some extent.

However, they fall short of acknowledging the experience of menstruation. Key aspects such as the physical and emotional journey throughout the menstrual cycle, cultural stigmas limiting access to essential resources, intersections with caste, education, sanitation workers, and the needs of women aged 25–49 years, prisoners, PwDs, menstruators during a humanitarian crisis and non-binary and transgender menstruators remain overlooked.

Managing menstrual waste is a complex challenge that requires a variety of strategies to address its environmental and health impacts. One approach focuses on reducing the overall volume of waste produced. This can be achieved by promoting the use of alternative menstrual hygiene products, such as reusable pads and menstrual cups, which not only lessen the amount of waste generated but also contribute to long-term cost savings for individuals. However, while promoting reusable menstrual products for environmental reasons, the lack of proper WASH infrastructure and persistent stigma can render their use unhygienic for the individual.

Sterilising menstrual waste is another important aspect of making it less hazardous. Chemical treatments and autoclaving technologies (meaning subjecting menstrual waste to high-pressure steam at elevated temperatures to sterilise it, making it safe for disposal) can effectively neutralise pathogens, ensuring safer disposal. Additionally, altering waste's physical nature through methods like incineration, deep burial, composting, and recycling can simplify management, diminish volume, and lessen environmental impact. By implementing these diverse strategies, various stakeholders can work towards more sustainable menstrual waste management practices that prioritise the health and dignity of individuals while minimising environmental impact (WaterAid India, 2019).

The time has come to broaden the conversation to include these vital dimensions and ensure comprehensive support for menstruating individuals and effective menstrual waste management.

Policy Recommendations

1. National Body – Menstrual Health

- a. Establishing a national body dedicated to addressing the menstrual health and well-being of all menstruators in India. This centralised initiative will facilitate ownership, allocate resources, and ensure the long-term sustainability of efforts related to this issue, thereby providing a robust framework for the multidimensional and intersectional aspects of menstrual policy development.

2. Inclusive Awareness Campaigns:

- a. Develop campaigns that go beyond product accessibility and affordability to include the social, physical, and emotional aspects of menstruation and menopause through a lifecycle approach.
- b. Inclusion of not only menstruating individuals but even men and other family members in the awareness campaigns.
- c. Prioritise attention to the menstrual challenges and needs of the most marginalised and missed-out communities to address cultural stigmas and intersecting challenges faced by overlooked groups such as sanitation workers, prisoners, persons with disabilities (PwDs), and non-binary and transgender individuals.

3. Targeted Support Programs:

- a. Tailor programs specifically for women aged 25–49 years, prisoners, PwDs, and those in humanitarian crises to ensure their unique needs are met.
- b. Implement policies that guarantee access to essential menstrual products and adequate facilities in these contexts.
- c. Skill training to make cloth pads.

4. Address the market failure around menstrual product access and affordability and sustainability

- a. Support and nurture innovation in small and medium-scale enterprises around sustainable products.
- b. Learn from the Goonj example and tap into India's textile industry surplus to connect and promote cloth pads as a viable and sustainable option.

5. Educational Institutes

- a. Include learning about the menstrual cycle and its different aspects in the school curriculum
- b. Provision of menstrual hygiene products, medical support for managing menstrual cramps, and counselling sessions.

6. Enhanced WASH Infrastructure:

- a. Taking insights from Goonj's work that connects menstrual awareness with grassroots action, it is essential to engage with menstruators in rural India and identify and address their WASH challenges.
- b. Prioritise the development of Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) infrastructure not only in education institutions but also in public spaces and informal workplaces to support the needs of the informal sector workers.
- c. Involve and encourage the most marginalised women and menstruators to create viable livelihood options from the work of awareness building and creating sustainable market conditions, especially in rural India.

7. Advanced Menstrual Waste Management:

- a. Promote the use of environmentally friendly menstrual products like reusable cloth pads and menstrual cups to reduce waste generation.
- b. Invest in technologies for safe sterilisation of menstrual waste, such as chemical treatments and autoclaving, to ensure its safe disposal.
- c. Explore various disposal methods, such as incineration, deep burial, composting, and recycling, to manage waste efficiently and reduce environmental impact.
- d. Implement policy interventions to safeguard the human rights of sanitation workers handling menstrual waste while also strengthening the implementation of producers' responsibility to involve menstrual pad-making companies in addressing this issue.

8. Comprehensive Policy Frameworks:

- a. Develop comprehensive policies that integrate menstrual hygiene and waste management into broader sexual and reproductive health frameworks.

9. Research and Innovation:

- a. Encourage research into innovative solutions for menstrual hygiene and waste management, considering local contexts and environmental sustainability.
- c. Support initiatives that foster collaboration between stakeholders, including government agencies, NGOs, and private sectors, to drive progress in this area.

By implementing these recommendations, policymakers can foster a supportive environment that respects the dignity of menstruating individuals, promotes sustainable practices, and addresses the multifaceted challenges of menstrual hygiene and waste management comprehensively.

References

- Babbar, K., & Ojha, M. (2023). Towards an inclusive national policy on menstrual health and hygiene. Observer Research Foundation.
<https://www.orfonline.org/research/towards-an-inclusive-national-policy-on-menstrual-health-and-hygiene>
- CARE International in Uganda. (2018). Ruby Cups: Girls in IMVEPi refugee settlement taking control. <http://womensa.dk/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Ruby-Cups-Girls-in-Imvepi-Refugee-Settlement-Taking-Control-03.12.18-Final-report.pdf>
- Diamond, C. (2022, August 15). Period poverty: Scotland first in world to make period products free. BBC Scotland News. <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-scotland-politics-51629880>
- Down to Earth (2023, November 28). Extreme weather 2023: India saw a disaster nearly every day from January-September. <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/climate-change/extreme-weather-2023-india-saw-a-disaster-nearly-every-day-from-january-september-93024>
- Euronews. (2022, December 15). Spain votes to approve a new law to introduce paid menstrual leave for painful periods.
<https://www.euronews.com/next/2022/12/15/spain-votes-to-approve-a-new-law-to-introduce-paid-menstrual-leave-for-painful-periods>
- Garg, S., & Anand, T. (2015). Menstruation related myths in India: Strategies for combating it. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, 4(2), 184–86.
<https://doi.org/10.4103/2249-4863.154627>
- Government of India. (2022). Women and men in India. Social Statistics Division. Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India.
- Government Equalities Office. (2019, July 23). Period poverty: Period poverty taskforce meets for the first time. Government Equalities Office.
<https://www.gov.uk/government/news/period-poverty-taskforce-meets-for-the-first-time#:~:text=The%20newly%20formed%20Period%20Poverty,around%20menstruation%20in%20the%20UK.>
- Gopakumar, K. (2022). Retaining the nonprofit mission: The case of social enterprise emergence in India from a traditional nonprofit. *ideas.repec.org*.
<https://ideas.repec.org/a/taf/entreg/v34y2022i1-2p110-136.html>
- Gupta, H. G., & Sivakami, M. (2024, May 28). World Menstrual Hygiene Day 2024: Menstrual hygiene in Indian prisons | Explained. *The Hindu*.
<https://www.thehindu.com/sci-tech/health/menstrual-hygiene-in-indian-prisons-explained/article68222812.ece>

Harad, T. (2023). Women prisoners face poor menstrual hygiene management, lack of adequate facilities. *The Wire*. <https://thewire.in/women/women-prisoners-face-poor-menstrual-hygiene-management-lack-of-adequate-facilities>

Hallad, J., Pundappanavar, B. I., Chokhandre, P. K., & Vatavati, S. R. (2023). Menstrual health and hygiene among adolescent girls in climate vulnerable areas in India. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. https://prku.uok.edu.in/Files/fb7d7958-7015-454e-8e81-0d536ab44bad/Menu/Pan_India_MHH_among_adolescent_girls_25042023_d5e1b7a4-da3a-48eb-91c4-8f88f6d68b9f.pdf

Hennegan, J., Winkler, I. T., Bobel, C., Keiser, D., Hampton, J., Larsson, G., Chandra-Mouli, V., Plesons, M., & Mahon, T. (2021). Menstrual health: A definition for policy, practice, and research. *Sexual and Reproductive Health Matters*, 29(1), 31–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26410397.2021.1911618>

Hirani, S. a. A. (2024). Barriers to women's menstrual hygiene practices during recurrent disasters and displacement: A qualitative study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21(2), 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21020153>

Kalia, S. (2023, April 30). Explained | Menstrual hygiene facilities in Indian schools. *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/sci-tech/health/explained-menstrual-hygiene-facilities-in-indian-schools/article66754551.ece>

Lopez, M. (2021). A study of the disposal of menstrual products. The University of Manchester.

https://hummedia.manchester.ac.uk/institutes/gdi/research/SIUYV_A5_Booklet_2021_WEB_Spreads.pdf

Malaviya, S. (2019). The mammoth task of managing menstrual waste in India. <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/blog/health/the-mammoth-task-of-managing-menstrual-waste-in-india-63376>

MacRae, E. R., Clasen, T., Dasmohapatra, M., & Caruso, B. A. (2019, August 1). "It's like a burden on the head": Redefining adequate menstrual hygiene management throughout women's varied life stages in Odisha, India. *Plos One*, 14(8): e0220114. doi: 0.1371/journal.pone.0220114

McCammon, E., Bansal, S., Hebert, L. E., Yan, S., Menendez, A., & Gilliam, M. (2020). Exploring young women's menstruation-related challenges in Uttar Pradesh, India, using the socio-ecological framework. *Sexual and Reproductive Health Matters*, 28(1): 291–301. doi: 10.1080/26410397.2020.1749342

McLaren, M. A., & Padhee, M. (2021). A sexual and reproductive health rights approach to menstruation. *Gender and Development*, 29(1), 131–50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13552074.2021.1885218>

Meadows, D. H., Meadows, D. L., Randers, J., & Behrens, W. W. (2018). The limits to growth. In *Green planet blues*, pp. 25–29. Routledge.

Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. (2023a). Draft National Menstrual Hygiene Policy, 2023.

<https://main.mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/Draft%20Menstrual%20Hygiene%20Policy%202023%20-For%20Comments.pdf>

Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. (2023b). Update on access to Menstrual Hygiene facilities. PIB Delhi.

<https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasframePage.aspx?PRID=1986698#:~:text=The%20draft%20Menstrual%20Hygiene%20Policy,to%20menstrual%20hygiene%20resources%20and>

Mondal, M. (2020). 'Padding Up during Crisis. Oxfam India.

https://www.oxfamindia.org/featuredstories/padding-up-during-crisis?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAjwps-zBhAiEiwALwsVYfymtI2fK3Z6wijLBstss8_4f59Ohgkq7PzD2a6VFMzmJptT7Fm4QhoCno4QAvD_BwE

Muthusamy, Sivakami (2019, June). Effect of menstruation on girls and their schooling, and facilitators of hygiene management in schools: Surveys in government schools in three states in India, 2015. *Journal of Global Health*, 9(1). doi: 10.7189/jogh.09.010408.

National Conference of State Legislatures. (2023, February 13). Period poverty: State actions to increase access to menstrual products. <https://www.ncsl.org/health/state-actions-to-increase-access-to-menstrual-products#:~:text=Federal%20Action&text=The%20Coronavirus%20Aid%2C%20Relief%2C%20and,Account%20or%20Health%20Savings%20Account>.

Odey, G. O., Amusile, O., Oghenetajiri, P. O., David, S., Adi, A., & Lucero-Prisno, D. E. (2021). Period during a pandemic: The neglected reality of Nigerian girls and women. *Public Health in Practice*, 2, 100196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhip.2021.100196>

Shulka, A., & Kulkarni, S. (2019, June 29). Harvest of uteruses. *Economic and Political Weekly*. <https://www.epw.in/journal/2019/29/commentary/harvest-uteruses.html>

Schmitt, M. L., Clatworthy, D., Ratnayake, R., Klaesener-Metzner, N., Roesch, E., Wheeler, E., & Sommer, M. (2017). Understanding the menstrual hygiene management challenges facing displaced girls and women: Findings from qualitative assessments in Myanmar and Lebanon. *Conflict and Health*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13031-017-0121-1>

Scottish Government Health Workforce Directorate. (2023, October 31). Interim National Menopause and Menstrual Health Policy for NHS Scotland. DL (2023) 28. <https://www.publications.scot.nhs.uk/files/dl-2023-28.pdf>

Smile Foundation. (2023, August 4). Importance of menstrual hygiene for girls in schools. <https://www.smilefoundationindia.org/blog/importance-of-menstrual-hygiene-for-girls-in-schools/>

Sommer, M., Chandraratna, S., Cavill, S., Mahon, T., & Phillips-Howard, P. (2016). Managing menstruation in the workplace: An overlooked issue in low- and middle-income countries. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-016-0379-8>

Subhalakshmi, N. (2020, September). Roadmap for women's economic empowerment with a focus on women in informal economy and in agriculture. UN Women.

Sukumar, D. (2020). Personal narrative: Caste is my period. In C. Bobel et al. (eds.). *The Palgrave Handbook of Critical Menstruation Studies*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-0614-7_13

The Economic Times. (2023, October 2). Why menstrual waste is proving to be a “big bloody mess” in India. *The Economic Times*. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/india/the-menstrual-waste-conundrum-in-india-and-why-its-proving-to-be-a-big-bloody-mess-for-sustainability/articleshow/104106414.cms>

Treisman, R. (2021, February 18). Period poverty: New Zealand will offer free sanitary products at schools to fight period poverty. <https://www.npr.org/2021/02/18/969105972/period-poverty-new-zealand-will-offer-free-sanitary-products-at-schools-to-fight-peri>

UNESCO Office, New Delhi. (2023). Menstrual health and hygiene management: A module for well-being through nutrition. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000385510>

UNFPA & WaterAid India. (2021). Menstrual health and hygiene management during emergencies: A framework for action in India. UNFPA. https://india.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/mhbm_and_emergenciesfinal_november_2021.pdf

UNICEF. (2020). Guidance note: Menstrual health & hygiene for girls and women with disabilities. <https://www.unicef.org/documents/menstrual-health-hygiene-girls-and-women-disabilities>

USAID GlobalWaters. (2022, May 28). Menstrual health and hygiene technical brief. *Globalwaters.org*. <https://www.globalwaters.org/resources/assets/menstrual-health-and-hygiene-technical-brief>

Vashisht, A., Pathak, R., Agarwalla, R., Patavegar, B.N., & Panda, M. (2018). School absenteeism during menstruation amongst adolescent girls in Delhi, India. *Journal of Family and Community Medicine*, 25: 163–68.

WaterAid India. (2019). Menstrual waste management. <https://www.wateraid.org/in/publications/menstrual-waste-management>

WaterAid India & UNFPA. (2022). Menstrual health & hygiene management in India. *WaterAid*. <https://www.wateraid.org/in/publications/menstrual-waste-management>

CDPP Honorary Governing Council

G Sudhir, IAS (Retd) is the Founder and Director of CDPP. He served as Special Chief Secretary in undivided Andhra Pradesh and was also Chairman of the 2015 Commission of Inquiry to study socio-economic and educational conditions of Muslims in Telangana.

Syed Adeeluddin is the Director of CDPP. He is a philanthropist and social worker juggling his family construction business alongside. He is an engineering graduate of Osmania University, and has completed his MBA (Finance).

Amir Ullah Khan is Research Director at CDPP and Editor of the Journal of Development Policy and Practice. A development economist and former civil servant, he is also Adjunct Professor at MCRHRDI of Government of Telangana.

Neelima Khetan is Managing Partner at Nous Consulting. A social sector advisor with experience in non-profits, CSR, sustainable and rural development, she has previously headed the CSR divisions for Coca-Cola, Vedanta Group and Hindustan Zinc.

Amitabh Kundu is currently Distinguished Fellow at Research and Information System for Developing Countries. He was Dean of School of Social Sciences, JNU. He also served as Chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee.

Saleema Razvi is Research Economist at Copenhagen Consensus Center. She has previously worked in organisations like Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations, Population Foundation of India and UNICEF.

Abdul Shaban Is Professor at Centre for Public Policy, Habitat and Human Development, School of Development Studies, TISS, Mumbai. He has also been visiting Professor/fellow at several leading universities such as the LSE, Muenster University, Erasmus University and Paris Diderot University.

Jeemol Unni is a Professor at Ahmedabad University. She is former Director and RBI Chair Professor of Economics at of Institute of Rural Management, Anand. A specialist in labour economics, she is Editorial Board member of Indian Journal of Labour Economics and Journal of Development Policy and Practice.

Aalok Wadhwa is a management professional with around three decades of experience working in FMCG, online and social media content, publishing and retail businesses. A graduate of St. Stephen's College, he has an MBA from IIM-B.

Sumaira Naser is a philanthropist, educationist and an environmentalist. She is also a patron for the 'Telangana Science Fair Academy' which promotes scientific temperament amongst youth, an advisor at the 'International Women's Startup Corridor' (IWSC) with a focus to promote women's health.

Rathin Roy is Distinguished Professor at the Kautilya School of Public Policy, GiTAM University, Hyderabad, and a former member of the Economic Advisory Council to the Prime Minister. He holds PhD and MPhil degrees in Economics from the University of Cambridge. He has taught at the Universities of Manchester and London.

RESEARCH TEAM

Amitabh Kundu is a Senior Fellow at WRI India and has been the chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee set up by the Ministry of Minority Affairs.

Soma Wadhwa is a development studies researcher with extensive experience as a media professional.

Nahia Hussain is Vice President (Policy Affairs) at CDPP with a Master's from the National Law School of India, Bangalore.

Anjana Divakar is the Executive Director of Public Policy Research and Operations at the Centre for Development Policy and Practice (CDPP).

Apoorva Ramachandra is a Research Associate at CDPP. She has a Master's degree in Economics from the Jindal School of Government and Public Policy.

Moumita Barman is a Research Associate at CDPP. She has a Master's degree in Public Policy and Governance from the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Hyderabad

Laldinmoi Pangamte is the Copy Editor of publications at CDPP. She has a PhD degree from the School of International Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi.

Ablaz Mohammed Schemnad is a Research Associate at CDPP. He has done his master's in Development Studies from Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Hyderabad with a semester from Sciences Po Lille, France.

Rashad Ullah Khan is a Senior Research Fellow at CDPP. Previously, he worked as an Academic Associate at the Kautilya School of Public Policy. He completed his Master's in Women's Studies from the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai.

Mohammed Zaid Khan is a Junior Fellow in Media and Communications at CDPP. He is pursuing his Bachelor's degree in Commerce Analytics from St. Mary's College, Hyderabad.

Mohammed Yaqoob Quraishi is the Manager of operations & Finance at CDPP. He has a degree in Commerce from Osmania University.

Our Publications

- Gender and Inclusion Series
- Citizenship Series
- Aata Hai Yaad Mujko Guzra Hua Zamana
- Muslims in Uttar Pradesh
- India's Infrastructure Challenges
- Journal of Development Policy and Practice
- Alfaz Ki Mehfil – Edition I, II, and III
- Introduction to International Finance
- Wajood-e- Muslim
- Agriculture in Telangana
- Daman-e-Gulchein

Series – 2022

- Situating Development of Muslims in Uttar Pradesh
- Education Challenges: Quality and Inclusion
- How Healthy is our Young Population?
- Muslim Women Tackling Vulnerability and Marginalisation

Series – 2023

- Internet Control and the Rise of Discrimination in India
- Agriculture in Telangana: from Plight to Pride
- The World's Biggest Country: India's Demographic Trajectory and its Impact on Muslims, the Parliament, and the Labour Market
- From Speech to Action: Exploring Hate Speech Origins, Impact, and Interventions from Multidisciplinary Perspectives

Series – 2024

- Diversity and Disparities: A study on Caste, Religion, Gender and Disability in Higher Education in India
- Workforce Participation in India: Where are the Women?

The CDPP brings out a quarterly working paper based on the research work being carried out here. These are published on our website www.cdpp.co.in and sent to a selected group for review, comments, and critique.

CENTRE FOR DEVELOPMENT POLICY AND PRACTICE

Serene Heights Building, #10-3-303, Masab Tank,
Hyderabad-500028, T.S., India

info@cdpp.co.in | www.cdpp.co.in | +91 9391581698